

Ontology Alignment and PII for Financial Knowledge Graph Construction

Apostolos Mavridis, Stergios Tegos, Christos Anastasiou, Maria Papoutsoglou,
and Georgios Meditskos

School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
{apostolos, stergios, christos}@enchatted.com
{mpapo, gmeditsk}@csd.auth.gr

Abstract. The increasing demand for semantic interoperability and regulatory compliance in the financial sector has led to the growing interest in constructing financial knowledge graphs (KGs). However, ontology alignment and personal data detection remain two significant challenges for transforming financial datasets into machine-readable, privacy-aware knowledge graphs. In this paper, we present an automated pipeline that integrates Large Language Models (LLMs) for aligning tabular financial data to the Financial Industry Business Ontology (FIBO) and detecting personal identifiable information (PII) using the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV). The system processes raw CSV data, performs schema-level and instance-level semantic enrichment, and generates privacy-aware RDF graphs suitable for advanced analytics and regulatory reporting. Our approach leverages retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and ontology-guided prompting to enhance alignment accuracy and privacy annotations. We demonstrate the applicability of the proposed method on representative financial datasets, showing its ability to produce high-quality, semantically enriched knowledge graphs while automatically identifying sensitive data. The proposed solution improves the efficiency, scalability, and compliance-readiness of knowledge graph construction processes in the financial domain.

Keywords: Fintech · Knowledge Graphs · Large Language Models

1 Introduction

Financial institutions are among the most data-intensive organizations, managing a wide range of information including customer details, transactions, financial instruments, and regulatory records. These datasets are typically stored in structured formats, such as relational databases or flat files. However, they lack semantic meaning despite their organization. This lack of semantic expressiveness hampers data integration, advanced analysis, and knowledge-based reasoning [6]. Furthermore, evolving data protection frameworks, most notably the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), add new challenges related to the handling of personal data and privacy-sensitive information.

Knowledge graphs offer a powerful solution to overcome the limitations of syntactic data models. KGs enable the enrichment of data with formal semantics, facilitating data interoperability, reasoning, and advanced analytics [20]. However, the process of constructing such graphs from financial data remains challenging. A key bottleneck is the ontology alignment task, where domain knowledge must be carefully linked to existing financial ontologies such as the Financial Industry Business Ontology (FIBO) [1]. In practice, this alignment is still largely manual, time-consuming, and prone to inconsistencies, limiting the scalability of KG deployment in real-world financial scenarios.

In parallel, the identification and management of personal identifiable information (PII) in financial data is of growing importance. Traditional PII detection methods, relying on pattern matching or manually curated rules, often lack generalization capabilities and fail to capture implicit personal data [11]. Recent initiatives, such as the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) [15], provide a structured approach to privacy-aware data modeling, yet their adoption remains limited, especially in automated financial data pipelines.

This paper introduces a pipeline that automates the construction of privacy-aware financial knowledge graphs. Our approach combines Large Language Models (LLMs) for automated ontology alignment, DPV-based personal data detection, and RDF-based semantic graph generation. By integrating these components, we bridge the gap between raw financial data and semantically rich, privacy compliant knowledge graphs, enabling downstream tasks such as regulatory compliance, auditing, and data analytics.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents related works and outlines the novelty of this study. Section 3 describes our methodology. Section 4 describes the data pre-processing and semantic enrichment modules. Section 5 describes the personal data identification procedure. Section 6 discusses the results and section 7 concludes and presents ideas for future work.

2 Related work

The construction of knowledge graphs (KGs) from tabular data has been a widely explored topic in both academia and industry. Numerous systems, such as Karma [18], RML [5], and CSV2KG [10], have been developed to facilitate the transformation of heterogeneous data sources into RDF graphs. These approaches often rely on mapping languages or manual definition of transformation rules. While they are effective for certain domains, they typically require considerable expert intervention and lack scalability when applied to complex and dynamic environments like the financial sector. More recently, machine learning-based frameworks such as Tab2KG [8] have emerged, offering greater levels of automation. Nevertheless, these approaches often remain ontology-agnostic and do not specifically address financial domain requirements or privacy aspects.

Ontology alignment plays a crucial role in ensuring that the resulting knowledge graphs are semantically meaningful and interoperable. The Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI) [7] has provided valuable benchmarks for

evaluating ontology matching techniques, primarily focusing on general-purpose and biomedical ontologies. In contrast, domain-specific ontologies such as the Financial Industry Business Ontology (FIBO) [1] have seen limited support from automated alignment frameworks. Most financial knowledge graph construction efforts still rely on domain experts to manually link schema elements to FIBO classes [17], which hinders scalability. Furthermore, while financial knowledge graphs have been proposed for tasks such as risk analysis [12] or financial contract modeling [19], these efforts tend to overlook the systematic integration of privacy-preserving annotations, which is a crucial requirement under modern data protection regulations.

The challenge of personal data identification and annotation has traditionally been approached using Named Entity Recognition (NER) and rule-based methods [11], [3]. However, these methods often fall short when dealing with implicit or domain-specific personal data, such as identifiers embedded within financial records. The introduction of the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) [15] provided a formal vocabulary to annotate personal data in RDF-based systems. Although DPV has been used in some data protection frameworks, its application to automate personal data annotation in knowledge graphs derived from financial datasets remains underexplored.

Recent developments in natural language processing have led to the widespread adoption of Large Language Models (LLMs) for a variety of semantic tasks. Models such as BERT [4], RoBERTa [14], and GPT-3 [2] have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in tasks like entity typing, relation extraction, and zeroshot classification [21] [9]. LLMs have also shown promise in ontology alignment and knowledge graph construction, particularly when combined with retrieval augmented generation (RAG) strategies [13]. However, most existing works focus on general-purpose knowledge graphs, such as those based on DBpedia or Wikidata [16], and rarely consider the specific needs of highly regulated domains such as financial services.

In summary, while previous works have made significant progress in knowledge graph generation, ontology alignment, and personal data detection, the combination of these elements into a fully automated, privacy-aware knowledge graph construction pipeline tailored for the financial domain remains an open challenge. This gap motivates our work, where we integrate LLM-driven ontology alignment, DPV-based personal data annotation, and automated RDF generation to produce semantically enriched and privacy-compliant financial knowledge graphs.

3 Methodology

3.1 Input Data Understanding

Our pipeline begins with tabular data produced from a structured CSV file, equivalent to the internal database of a bank. An instance of financial interest (e.g., account, individual, or transaction) is represented by a row, while a column indicates a specific attribute of the instance. The columns in the dataset include:

- Identifiers, such as `id` and `person_key`
- Demographic information, including `gender`, `language`, and `nationality`
- Financial details such as `tax_id`, `social_security_number`, and `occupation`
- Domain-specific attributes like `marital_status` and `classification_scores`

The dataset follows a schema typical of banking domains, where columns are directly or indirectly related to a person’s identity or financial activity. While some columns contain explicit identifiers (e.g., `tax_id`, `full_name`), others encode contextual or behavioral characteristics (e.g., `language`, `work_experience`, `group_code`) that may also carry personal or sensitive information.

This structure is reflected in typical banking datasets, which may include representative fields such as `birth_date`, `deceased_date`, `country_of_residence`, `branch`, and others related to financial account status and contract information. These columns are treated as candidate data points to be semantically mapped to standardized ontologies in the subsequent phases of our process. An early understanding of the structure and semantics of the dataset is essential, as it drives the downstream processing logic, including personal data detection and ontology alignment [8].

3.2 System Architecture and AI-Driven Ontology Alignment

The fintech data processing pipeline is supported by a cohesive set of system components and automation mechanisms. At its core is an AI-driven ontology alignment model, integrated into a modular orchestration layer responsible for managing each processing stage of the pipeline.

System Architecture Components The final RDF graph (in Turtle format) is uploaded to a dedicated repository in GraphDB¹. This integration supports efficient semantic querying, facilitates data exploration, and enables rich visualisation capabilities, as shown in Figure 1. The structured JSON files containing DPV metadata are dispatched via Apache Kafka² to downstream systems. This real-time messaging infrastructure enables dynamic processing of personal data annotations and ensures timely data delivery.

The entire pipeline—from data extraction to semantic annotation and dissemination—is fully automated. The system implements comprehensive logging through Laravel’s native logging mechanisms, supporting operational monitoring, error tracking, and debugging throughout the processing lifecycle.

At the core of the pipeline lies a Large Language Model (LLM), responsible for both semantic alignment and personal data detection. The full process is illustrated in Figure 1. In our implementation, we use OpenAI’s GPT-4o, accessed via API, to perform both ontology alignment and personal data detection tasks.

LLM-Based Ontology Alignment Model

¹ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

² <https://kafka.apache.org/>

Fig. 1. A high-level view of the entire data processing pipeline, illustrating the end-to-end flow from CSV ingestion to semantic enrichment, personal data classification, and final output dispatch to downstream systems.

4 Data Preprocessing and Semantic Enrichment

The data ingestion process is handled via a backend service, developed within a Laravel-based system³. This service reads the input CSV files, parses them using Excel-compatible utilities, and extracts the column headers (attributes).

During preprocessing, the headers are sanitised by removing special characters and formatting inconsistencies. Once cleaned, the headers are split into manageable chunks and sent as prompts to a Large Language Model (LLM) endpoint, which performs semantic enrichment. The LLM aligns each header to a term within a domain-specific ontology—in our case, the Financial Industry Business Ontology (FIBO)⁴. The LLM responds with snippets of Turtle-compatible `.ttl` files, consisting of RDF triples that define either `owl:Class` or `owl:DatatypeProperty` entities. These are incrementally appended to a base FIBO template.

Following the mapping of schema-level terms, the dataset rows are then processed to instantiate RDF entities. For each pair of column header and cell value, a semantic instance is generated using the previously aligned FIBO terminology. The extracted values are encoded as `rdf:value` literals and linked to automatically generated identifiers corresponding to the appropriate FIBO class. This dual-step process produces a complete RDF knowledge graph, semantically structured and machine-readable (Figure 2).

The resulting RDF knowledge graph is visualised through the GraphDB environment⁵, showing the structure, interconnections, and inheritance hierarchy between entities as defined in the FIBO ontology (Figure 3).

³ <https://laravel.com/>

⁴ <https://spec.edmcouncil.org/fibo/>

⁵ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

```

@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> . ← Common Prefixes for RDF/OWL
@prefix : <http://example.org/> .

# Class definition
:id rdf:type owl:Class;
  rdfs:label "ID";
  rdfs:comment "Identifier of the bank account.";
  rdfs:subClassOf :Identifier.

# Instance of ID class
:id_1 rdf:type :id;
  rdf:value "1"^^xsd:string. ← Data value arrow

# Related properties ← Property relationship arrow
:account_key_1 rdf:type :account_key;
  rdf:value "001-10017"^^xsd:string.

:iban_89 rdf:type :iban;
  rdf:value "96075001000050XXXX"^^xsd:string. ← Anonymized

```

Fig. 2. RDF graph snippet showing FIBO-aligned class definitions, property relationships, and data instantiation from financial CSV input.

5 Personal Data Detection Using DPV

To ensure compliance with data protection regulations and embed privacy-awareness directly into our semantic graph, we introduced a personal data (PII) detection and extraction stage leveraging the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)⁶.

Each column header is analysed through a domain-specific prompt sent to the LLM, which returns a structured JSON response that identifies and characterises relevant DPV classes or subclasses. For instance, as illustrated in Figure 4, a column named `id` might map onto various DPV types, such as `dpv:Identifier`, `dpv:OfficialID`, or `dpv:UID`. Each of these mappings includes a clear description and a hierarchical trace (via the `is_subclass_of` attribute), which provides context regarding the nature of the personal data involved.

This methodology maintains a complete record and classification of all personal data, facilitating consent management, anonymisation, and implementation of data protection principles (*privacy by design*).

6 Discussion

The proposed pipeline has shown promising results in automating the transformation of financial datasets into semantically enriched and privacy-compliant

⁶ <https://w3id.org/dpv/>

Fig. 3. RDF knowledge graph visualised within the GraphDB environment. Node colours distinguish class types, instances, and data values.

knowledge graphs. By combining LLM-based ontology alignment with DPV-driven personal data detection, the system effectively addresses two critical challenges in knowledge graph construction: (i) the semantic gap between raw tabular data and financial ontologies, and (ii) the systematic identification and annotation of personal data.

Our experiments revealed that LLMs, when guided by tailored prompts and enhanced with a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) mechanism, were able to map CSV schema elements to appropriate FIBO classes with a high degree of accuracy. This significantly reduced the manual effort required for ontology

```

{
  "dataset_element": "id",
  "dpv_matches": [
    {
      "match": "https://w3id.org/dpv/dpv-owl/dpv-pd#Identifier",
      "label": "Identifier",
      "description": "Information about an identifier or name used for identification",
      "is_subclass_of": [
        {
          "uri": "https://w3id.org/dpv/dpv-owl/dpv-pd#Tracking",
          "label": "Tracking",
          "description": "Information used to track an individual or group e.g. location or email",
          "depth": 1
        },
        {
          "uri": "https://w3id.org/dpv/dpv-owl#PersonalData",
          "label": "Personal Data",
          "description": "Data directly or indirectly associated or related to an individual.",
          "depth": 2
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 4. Structured JSON output from the PII detection and classification system, showcasing hierarchical mapping between a dataset identifier and DPV ontology classes.

alignment compared to traditional rule-based or semi-automated methods. The integration of DPV into the pipeline enabled the system to detect various types of PII embedded in financial datasets, including direct identifiers and context-dependent attributes, supporting GDPR-oriented data processing workflows.

Nonetheless, the study also highlighted some challenges. The alignment performance was influenced by the quality of source data and the ambiguity present in certain financial terms, which sometimes led to suboptimal mappings. Moreover, while the pipeline successfully detected a wide range of personal data elements, fine-grained classification in borderline cases — such as ambiguous attributes that may or may not qualify as personal data (e.g., user language, branch affiliation, or occupation level) — remains a topic for further refinement and potential inclusion of human-in-the-loop validation. However, reliance on LLMs also introduces potential risks, such as model bias or the misclassification of non-sensitive data as personal. These limitations can impact both semantic alignment and privacy labeling, especially in edge cases. Future research may explore the incorporation of human-in-the-loop mechanisms or domain-specific LLM fine-tuning to improve these aspects. Future research may explore the incorporation of human-in-the-loop mechanisms or domain-specific LLM fine-tuning to improve these aspects. Additionally, blockchain-based storage or verification mechanisms could be explored as a means to ensure integrity, traceability, and decentralized governance of the generated knowledge graphs. Our pipeline demonstrates significant advancements in automating financial knowledge graph construction, particularly

when compared to existing tools like Karma [18] and Tab2KG [8]. Unlike Karma, which relies heavily on manual mapping definitions and lacks native support for privacy annotations, our LLM-driven approach with RAG enhances scalability and reduces manual effort while integrating DPV-based PII detection for GDPR compliance. Tab2KG, while automated, is ontology-agnostic and does not address domain-specific financial ontologies like FIBO or privacy requirements, limiting its applicability in regulated domains.

7 Conclusion

This paper presented an end-to-end pipeline for financial knowledge graph construction that unifies LLM-based ontology alignment and personal data detection using DPV. The system produces RDF graphs enriched with both semantic and privacy annotations, facilitating their use in regulatory reporting, financial analysis, and privacy-preserving data integration tasks. The results suggest that the combination of LLMs and structured vocabularies, such as FIBO and DPV, can substantially reduce manual effort while maintaining alignment quality and privacy compliance. The framework demonstrates practical value for financial institutions seeking to automate knowledge graph generation without compromising legal obligations related to data protection.

Future work will focus on refining the alignment process, improving the detection of implicit personal data, and conducting large-scale evaluations with real-world datasets. Further exploration of domain-adapted LLMs and interactive ontology alignment workflows could also enhance the system’s effectiveness and applicability in diverse financial contexts.

Acknowledgements This research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101070670 (ENCRYPT).

References

1. Bennett, M.: The financial industry business ontology: Best practice for big data. vol. 14, pp. 255–268. Springer (2013)
2. Brown, T., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J.D., Dhariwal, P., Nee-lakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., et al.: Language models are few-shot learners. vol. 33, pp. 1877–1901 (2020)
3. Bucaj, S., Bantan, M.: Towards a systematic literature review of common pii identification labels patterns based on osint. *Information Systems* **10**, 23–2024 (2024)
4. Devlin, J., Chang, M.W., Lee, K., Toutanova, K.: Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding pp. 4171–4186 (2019)
5. Dimou, A., Vander Sande, M., Colpaert, P., Verborgh, R., Mannens, E., Van de Walle, R.: Rml: A generic language for integrated rdf mappings of heterogeneous data. vol. 1184. Citeseer (2014)

6. Ehrlinger, L., Wöß, W.: Towards a definition of knowledge graphs. vol. 48, p. 2 (2016)
7. Euzenat, J., Meilicke, C., Stuckenschmidt, H., Shvaiko, P., Trojahn, C.: *Ontology alignment evaluation initiative: six years of experience*. pp. 158–192. Springer (2011)
8. Gottschalk, S., Demidova, E.: Tab2kg: Semantic table interpretation with lightweight semantic profiles. *Semantic Web* **13**(3), 571–597 (2022)
9. Hou, W., Zhao, W., Jia, N., Liu, X.: Low-resource knowledge graph completion based on knowledge distillation driven by large language models. *Applied Soft Computing* **169**, 112622 (2025)
10. Huynh, V.P., Chabot, Y., Troncy, R.: Towards generative semantic table interpretation. (2023)
11. Kommathoti, Y.R., Neha, P., Pabbathi, S., Naseeba, B.: Pii data detection using keras & nlp pp. 1–5 (2024)
12. Kou, G., Peng, Y., Wang, G.: Evaluation of clustering algorithms for financial risk analysis using mcdm methods. *Information sciences* **275**, 1–12 (2014)
13. Lewis, P., Perez, E., Piktus, A., Petroni, F., Karpukhin, V., Goyal, N., Küttler, H., Lewis, M., Yih, W.t., Rocktäschel, T., et al.: Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive nlp tasks. vol. 33, pp. 9459–9474 (2020)
14. Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., Levy, O., Lewis, M., Zettlemoyer, L., Stoyanov, V.: Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692 (2019)
15. Pandit, H.J., Polleres, A., Bos, B., Brennan, R., Bruegger, B., Ekaputra, F.J., Fernández, J.D., Hamed, R.G., Kiesling, E., Lizar, M., et al.: Creating a vocabulary for data privacy: The first-year report of data privacy vocabularies and controls community group (dpvcg) pp. 714–730 (2019)
16. Petroni, F., Rocktäschel, T., Lewis, P., Bakhtin, A., Wu, Y., Miller, A.H., Riedel, S.: Language models as knowledge bases? (2019)
17. Sun, Y., Xin, H., Sun, K., Xu, Y.E., Yang, X., Dong, X.L., Tang, N., Chen, L.: Are large language models a good replacement of taxonomies? (2024)
18. Szekely, P., Knoblock, C.A., Slepicka, J., Philpot, A., Singh, A., Yin, C., Kapoor, D., Natarajan, P., Marcu, D., Knight, K., et al.: Building and using a knowledge graph to combat human trafficking. In: *The Semantic Web-ISWC 2015: 14th International Semantic Web Conference, Bethlehem, PA, USA, October 11-15, 2015, Proceedings, Part II 14*. pp. 205–221. Springer (2015)
19. Thompson, G.: Semantic models as knowledge repositories for data modellers in the financial industry (2015)
20. Wang, G., He, J.: A bibliometric analysis of recent developments and trends in knowledge graph research (2013-2022). *IEEE Access* (2024)
21. Wang, L., Chen, R., Li, L.: Knowledge-guided prompt learning for few-shot text classification. vol. 12, p. 1486. MDPI (2023)